

Revisiting the ‘productivity puzzle’ of female scholarship

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Abstract

In recent years special attention was given to identify gaps in scientific productivity and impact between women and men. These studies contributed to our understanding of how social, economic, inequity, and gaps in career opportunities contributed to the increasing gaps in advancement, productivity and impact between men and women in science. In this study we focused on tracking the differences between men and women’s productivity and impact with the same academic age, single authorship in the same disciplines. We sought to demonstrate the dynamics of females and males’ publications and impact over time by analyzing number of publications and citations by academic age and by selected discipline. Our contribution is mainly the addition of two parameters: academic age and single authorship analysis. Our findings show, that except for Nursing, which is already dominated by female authors, all the disciplines we studied showed that male authors receive more citations as single authors than females. This study demonstrates that gaps in impact exist even when single authorship and same academic age are identical. This is concerning since these gaps seem to be inscribed from early career and as previous studies showed, continue through the scientific careers of females and males.

Introduction

This article tests female scholarly productivity and citation strength by academic age, with examples from six disciplines. Bibliometricians and social scientists have extensively studied the disparities and slow advances of female academics in terms of productivity (numbers of publications) and recognition (citations and promotions) (a sample: Fox, 1983 and 2012; Cole & Zuckerman, 1984; Fox & Faver, 1985; Long, 1990 and 1992; Long & Fox, 1995; Xie & Shauman, 1998; Stack, 2002; Prpic, 2004; Abramo et al., 2007; Ceci & Williams, 2011; West et al., 2013; van den Besselaar & Sandstrom, 2017). Advances have been made in female representation on faculties of universities and colleges. In the United States, the percentage of all female instructors increased to 51% by 2020, with tenured, doctoral faculty at 38% women, 52% men (NCSES, 2022), up from 18.8% in 1980 (Hyer, 1984). The rise in numbers spur us to revisit the ‘productivity puzzle’ to examine outputs by age cohort.

Zuckerman & Cole (2004), returning to the subject they had written about in 1984 (Cole & Zuckerman), noted that “more than 50 studies of scientists in various fields show that women publish less than men...” (p.217) with differences across fields. Zuckerman and Cole found correlations between gender and productivity as roughly constant since the 1920s, creating a ‘productivity puzzle’. Van den Besselaar and Sandstrom (2017) noted that “[q]uite some literature exists on gendered publication difference.... a well-known and widely accepted observation that male researchers are more productive than female researchers....” (p. 1). Their work supported earlier work: they showed female researchers publishing 67% the amount of male output. The productivity puzzle has been confirmed in the social sciences (van Arensbergen et al. 2012); in Economics (Ferber & Brun, 2011); in agriculture, biology, Chemistry, Computer Sciences, and humanities (van den Besselaar & Sandstrom); and life sciences (Tomaskovic-Devey, 2005). The gap persists across borders, having been found in

Canada (Lariviere et al., 2011); Italy (Abramo et al. 2009); and Sweden (van den Besselaar & Sandstrom, 2017); although, interestingly, not in China (Tao et al, 2017).

Gingras et al. (2008) showed that overall research productivity rises rapidly for academic faculty between 28 and 40. Productivity continues rising at a slower rate between 41 and 50 and stabilizes at 50 for the rest of their career. Xia and Shauman (1998) reported that the productivity gap for women was most visible in the early stages of a researcher's career for the timeframe covered (1970-1990), suggesting that the gap begins early and, over time, becomes perhaps too great to close. Abramo et al. (date) report that women are underrepresented as authors of single-authored papers.

While the gap persists, some glimmers of improvement for women appear in the literature. Xie & Shauman (1998) found female productivity differences declined from about 60 percent of male counterparts in the late 1960s to 75 to 80 percent in the late 1980s and early 1990s, finding confirmed by van den Besselaar and Sandstrom (2017). Abramo et al. (2009) found that women lag in representation among top scientists, but van Arensbergen et al. (2012) found that, among the young generation in the social sciences, the publication differences disappear in the 2003-2005 timeframe. Van den Besselaar and Sandstrom (2017) confirmed this finding that women were as productive as men in a number of fields; they did not find a difference in age.

We hypothesized that a larger number of women in academic life, along with institutional efforts to support female faculty, would result in further closing of the productivity gap. Moreover, improved measures are needed: the United Nations has paid heed to the low percentages of female representation in science careers. According to the U.N. (date), women are consistently underfunded in scientific research; they represent 33.3% of all researchers globally; and only 12% of national science academies memberships are women. To encourage global action in developing and providing equal opportunities to women in science, the UN established the 'International Day of Women and Girls in Science' which occurs annually in February. This article provides measures to aid accounting for SDG success.

Methods and data

Given divergent findings in academic productivity among young women scholars, this article focuses on productivity by academic age of female authors. The choice to focus on academic age stems from the need to examine whether there is a change in participatory levels through time, especially to examine if more females are entering and thriving in certain scientific fields. Finally, we also sought to demonstrate the dynamics of females and males' publications and impact over time by analyzing number of publications and citations by academic age and by selected discipline. Our contribution is mainly the addition of two parameters: academic age and single authorship analysis. Data collected from the Web of Science are limited to authors with at least one single-author publication affiliated to an academic institution in the United States. This choice allows analysis of differences in the number of publications, academic age and citations received in the selected disciplines over the 10 years from 2011-2021. Academic age is defined as the time difference between the date of the first publication and last publication on record. With these data, we calculate academic age based on a researchers' entire publication record, including multi-authored publications. The 74,815 authors that have produced a single authored publication between 2011 and 2021 have collectively produced 4,095,035 publications across their entire careers to date. With the exception of calculating the academic age all other analyses are based on the single authored publications. From Web of Science, we extracted all single-authored publications. We included all publication types including articles, reviews, letters etc. for a full list of publication types please see Appendix A. we limited the dataset to publications with an address in the United States and included all institution's types

that are covered in Web of Science. For a full list of institution types please see Appendix B. all publications included in this study were published between 2011 and 2021. The initial search yielded 145,291 publications. We disambiguated those 145,291 publications across their 74,815 authors using a proprietary algorithm similar to that used to create Web of Science Author Profiles.

Table 1. Total numbers of single authored papers by year

<i>Initial Search Results</i>	<i>Number of female, single-authored papers</i>	<i>Number of male, single-authored papers</i>
2011	3762	7505
2012	3785	7732
2013	4084	7773
2014	4084	8083
2015	4243	7934
2016	4547	8163
2017	4812	8218
2018	4665	8000
2019	4903	8243
2020	3678	5533
2021	3176	5097

For the 74,815 author profiles we excluded those with only first initials and ran the longest name variant of those remaining against the NamSor API, which returned an estimated gender. The NamSor API is a commonly used tool for gender estimation, with NamSor reporting precision and recall figures of 98.41% and 99.28% respectively for European names. Independent studies have explored the accuracy of gender detection tools and found the NamSor API to be the most accurate in the European focused names. For Namsor related API, please see Appendix C.

Following gender estimation, the resulting dataset consisted of 66,868 authors with a single author publication meeting the inclusion criteria. For those authors we calculated their academic age (last year – first year) based on their entire career profile. We chose to include single authorship purposely. This enabled us to distil and more accurately identify any gaps we might find whereas all authors are single authors, in the same discipline and the same academic age.

Disciplinary focus

For this study we chose to analyze six web of science categories: Chemistry; Computer Science; Economics; Nursing; Physics and Psychiatry. The main rationale for choosing this particular combination of disciplines was to include areas of science that represent a variety of female participation levels. Nursing, for example is traditionally a ‘female dominated’ research area, while Physics is seen to be a ‘male dominated’ research area.

Overall trends

Females are single authoring papers much earlier in academic age than males

We calculated the academic age of all authors in our dataset by taking the difference between the date of their first publication and the date of their last publication. Interestingly, our data show that there are consistently more male single authors than female single authors across all our studied disciplines. However, it should be noted that the academic age of females is lower than that of the males in all disciplines. This could indicate that females are publishing as single authors earlier in their career or that women have shorter careers. For example, in psychiatry the median academic age of males and females is 27 and 17 respectively. This means that males publish single authored papers at a much later stage than females and that males at the beginning of their career publish more in a group than they do later in their career. The same trends can be seen across all disciplines.

Figure 1. median academic age by discipline

Considering that our study included only single authored papers, we examined the fraction of female authorships in the disciplines studied and compared it to the fraction of unique female authors in our data. We found that across all disciplines the fraction of female authors is slightly higher than the fraction of authorships. This indicates females produce marginally less than their expected share of single authorships compared to males. Nursing is a discipline where we see the least gap between authors and authorships, also a discipline that is dominated by women (see figure 2).

Figure 2. female authorship vs. authors by discipline

Female participation

Our data show that across most of the studied disciplines, female participation is growing steadily. Female single-authored publication count in Computer Science, Economics, Physics, and psychiatry is showing modest but steady growth over the time period. Chemistry is the only discipline that demonstrates a decrease, which is moderate and only between 2019-2021. In Nursing we see a high fraction of female single-authored publications which is stable over the time period (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. female fraction across disciplines

Trends by discipline

In this section we describe the main findings per discipline. For each discipline we examined the density of females and males by academic year and the number of citations per paper received by females and males by academic age.

Chemistry

In Chemistry, we see a strong contribution from female single authors early in their careers, especially within academic ages of 1-18. Figure 4 demonstrates the gender density of females and males single authors by academic age.

Figure 4. female/male authors normalized publication volume by academic age in Chemistry

Compared to males, relatively more women seem to publish as single authors in the first decade or so of their careers. Later in their careers, women are seen to publish less as single authors. According to our data men publish as single authors similarly in the first and second half of their career. While, in absolute terms, there are fewer female single authorships than male single authorships in the early academic age groups, relatively, the females are weighted to these early years. It follows that males and females reach a crossing point in the relative publication rate close to the 25th academic year, where both groups publish as single authors at similar rates. This is followed by a relative higher fraction of male single authored publications compared to female single authored publications in the later academic years. Interestingly, when examining the numbers of citations per publication for the single authored papers by gender and academic age (see figure 5). We noticed a significant gap between number of citations of single female authors and of single male authors. This could be the result of the overall higher rate of single male authors overall.

Figure 5. female/male citations per publication by academic age in Chemistry

The distribution of single authored publications across academic age groups is more weighted to the early years for females than it is for males. There could be a number of factors contributing to this phenomenon and some of those may influence the number of citations a work collects. One likely possibility is that there are fewer females active in the later academic age groups, which is consistent with findings presented in other studies. There could also be a contribution from a difference in publishing patterns, for example males may develop networks earlier in their career and so co-author with those groups in preference to single authorship.

Physics

In the Physics we see slightly more female single authors in early career ages with a spike during their 16-18 year. As career age matures there is less female single-authored papers which is seen in the 32nd year academic age forward (see figure 6). This is similar to our findings in Chemistry, in Physics whereas more pronounced weighting of single authored publications to the early academic years for females than males. This peak in the number of single authored publications happens at 13-15 and 16-18 career years for both males and females respectively.

Figure 6. female/male authors normalized publication volume by academic age in Physics

Another similarity between Chemistry and Physics is the low number of citations received by single authored female papers compared to their male counter parts across academic ages. As can be seen from Figure 7 the number of citations per publication is lower for female single authored publications compared to males' (see figure 7). This seems to be consistent even in academic ages where females are publishing as single authors more than males do. This is an interesting finding to note as it does indicate some gender gaps traced by citations impact. It should also be noted that our data also show that in Physics, unlike other disciplines that we analyzed, there are fewer single authored papers overall so although the trends remain similar, the number of publications is fewer.

Figure 7. female/male citations per publication by academic age in Physics

Computer Science

Similar trends are seen in Computer Science. Female single authorship is seen between 1-18 academic years and is especially strong between 13-18 academic years (see figure 8). Starting at approximately the 20th academic year, the male and female distributions of single authored papers across academic age groups crosses, with males having more weight than females in the later academic years.

Figure 8. female/male density in single authored papers by academic age in Computer Science

As seen in Chemistry and Physics, also in Computer Science, male’s single authored papers receive more citations regardless of their academic age even when the number of single authored female publications is higher (see figure 9).

Figure 9. female/male citations per publication by academic age in Computer Science

Economics

In Economics we see a similar trend in single authorships, the distribution of single authored publications is more weighted to the early years for females than males (see figure 10).

Figure 10. female/male density in single authored papers by academic age in Economics

However, unlike previous disciplines we analyzed, the received citations in Economics are more variable. The trend here is that the number of citations to single authored publications produced by female authors exceeds those to single authored publications produced by male authors in some academic age groups. Generally, the number of citations per publication is approximately the same across the academic age groups. This is in contrast to the other fields of research which appear to be less balanced (see figure 11).

Figure 11. female/male citations per publication by academic age in Economics

Psychiatry

Psychiatry is an interesting area since it demonstrates slightly different trends than others observed thus far. Similarly, to other fields we have discussed, the distribution of single authored publications is more heavily weighted to the early academic years for females than males (see figure 12).

Figure 12. female/male density in single authored papers by academic age in Psychiatry

However, our data show that single authored female publications receive higher number of citations per publication in many of the academic age groups. (See figure 13). It is unclear why Psychiatry differs from the other fields of research.

Figure 13. female/male citations per publication by academic age in Psychiatry

Nursing

We chose to analyze Nursing as a discipline because it is normally dominated by female authorship. The purpose of this choice was to discover whether in a discipline that includes more female authors we might see some of the trends we've seen in previous disciplines. In Nursing, we see a strong contribution to single authorship during the 1-3 career years period, for both males and females. This drops dramatically in the next career age brackets onwards. There are many interconnected possibilities for the origin of this large step. One possibility is a high attrition rate of Nursing researchers in the first three career years. Additionally, it might be that many authors begin as single authors and later manage to build a network, maybe within their departments / hospitals, and begin publishing co-authored papers. The unique phenomenon in Nursing is that we see a very similar distribution of single authored publications across the academic age categories for males and females (see figure 14).

Figure 14. female/male density in single authored papers by academic age in Nursing

In addition to the above observations, there is a substantial gap between female single authored publications, which receive more citations per publication, and male single authored publications, which is sustained across all academic age groups. In the case of Nursing, female

single authored papers receive more citations than those of males across academic ages despite the similar production rates of both genders. This is again, something to note. Although we cannot statistically explain the reason this is occurring, in the case of Nursing, females receive more citations than man across the board (See figure 15).

Figure 15. female/male citations per publication by academic age in Nursing

Discussion

In this paper we chose to focus on 3 facets (1) Gender (2) Career / Academic age (3) Single authorship. We chose a variety of disciplines in order to capture any gaps or trends across the sciences. These included Chemistry, Physics, Computer Science, Psychiatry, Economics and Nursing. The common trends we observed are that there are more single authored female publications in early career ages which seems to be consistent across disciplines. This trend changes in mid-career age where we see more single authored male publications than females. For late career ages, we have observed an overall reduction in single authored papers overall and in general more male single authored papers than females. This is an interesting finding which although cannot be explained by the data, should be studied further. The main question this finding poses is why are more females publishing single authored papers at the beginning of their career than males do? When considering the fact that this is found across disciplines it is something that should be explored further.

The second finding in this study is that female single authored papers receive less citations per paper even in early career stages when they publish more. This is true across disciplines except Nursing. Nursing is a research area that is dominated by female authored. Therefore, the question posed why female single authored papers would receive less citations in the various disciplines except the one where they dominate authorship.

The third finding is that our data shows females at younger academic age across fields. As can be seen above, female participation is growing steadily. Female single-authored publication count across disciplines showing modest but steady female participation growth over the time period. Chemistry is the only discipline that demonstrates a decrease, which is moderate and only between 2019-2021.

Conclusions

Our study shows that females are slowly but steadily entering the research arena across disciplines. Females publish more single authored papers than males in early career ages and that in mid- and later-career ages this trend changes whereas males publish more single authored papers than females. We also showed that citations per paper are lower for single authored female papers than males even in years when they publish more except for Nursing. The lower citations per papers in most disciplines except Nursing could be a factor of the distribution of females and males in the field itself. The reasons for the first observation cannot be deciphered from the data and should be studied further.

References

- Abramo, G., D'Angelo, C., & Caprasecca, A. (2009). Gender differences in research productivity: A bibliometric analysis of the Italian academic system. *Scientometrics*, 79(3), 517-539.
- Ceci, S. J., & Williams, W. M. (2011). Understanding current causes of women's underrepresentation in science. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(8), 3157-3162.
- Cole, J. R., & Zuckerman, H. (1984). The productivity puzzle. *Advances in motivation and achievement*, 2, 217-58.
- Fox, M. F. (1983). Publication productivity among scientists: A critical review. *Social studies of science*, 13(2), 285-305.
- Fox, M., Faver, C. (1985). Men, Women, and Publication Productivity: Patterns Among Social Work Academics.
- Gingras, Y., Lariviere, V., Macaluso, B., & Robitaille, J. P. (2008). The effects of aging on researchers' publication and citation patterns. *PloS one*, 3(12), e4048.
- Ginther, D. K., & Kahn, S. (2021, May). Women in Academic Economics: Have We Made Progress?. In *AEA Papers and Proceedings* (Vol. 111, pp. 138-42).
- Leahey, E. (2006). Gender difference in productivity: research specialization as a missing link. *Gender and Society* 20(6), 754-780.
- NCSSES <https://nces.nsf.gov/pubs/nsf21321/report/academic-careers>
- Tao, Y., Hong, W. & Ma, Y. Gender Differences in Publication Productivity Among Academic Scientists and Engineers in the U.S. and China: Similarities and Differences. *Minerva* 55, 459-484 (2017).
- Tomaskovic-Devey, D. Women's work: gender equality vs. hierarchy in the life sciences. *Adm. Sci. Q.* 50, 661-662 (2005).
- Van Arensbergen, P., van der Weijden, I., van den Besselaar, P. (2012). Gender differences in scientific productivity: a persisting phenomenon? *Scientometrics* 93, 857-868.
- West, J. D., Jacquet, J., King, M., Correll, S. J. & Bergstrom, C. T. *PLoS ONE* 8, e66212 (2013).
- Xie, Y., & Shauman, K. A. (1998). Sex differences in research productivity: New evidence about an old puzzle. *American sociological review*, 847-870.
- Zuckerman, H. (1984) Performance of gender detection tools: a comparative study of name-to-gender inference services. 109(3) July 2021 Journal of the Medical Library Association
- How accurate are gender detection tools in predicting the gender for Chinese names? A study with 20,000 given names in Pinyin format. *J Med Libr Assoc.* 2022 Apr 1; 110(2): 205-211.

Appendix A – Web of Science Document Types

Article
Abstract of Published Item
Art Exhibit Review
Bibliography
Biographical-Item
Book
Book Chapter
Book Review
Chronology
Correction
Correction, Addition
Dance Performance Review
Data Paper
Database Review
Discussion
Early Access (Web of Science Core Collection only)
Editorial Material
Excerpt
Fiction, Creative Prose
Film Review
Hardware Review
Item About an Individual
Letter
Meeting Abstract
Meeting Summary
Music Performance Review
Music Score
Music Score Review
News Item
Note
Poetry
Proceedings Paper
Record Review
Reprint
Retracted Publication
Retraction
Review
Script
Software Review
TV Review, Radio Review
TV Review, Radio Review, Video
Theater Review

Appendix B – Indexed Institution Types

Organization Type	Description
Academic	Primary function is education, degrees awarded. Name contains University, College, URL ends in .edu. Medical research institutes that are part of an academic organization should be Academic (e.g., Harvard).

Organization Type	Description
Academic System	Parent organization of a group of universities or colleges (e.g., University of Wisconsin System).
Corporate	Business, legal entity, has a board of directors, a stock symbol, URL ends in .com (e.g., Pfizer Australia).
Government	State owned or operated organizations. Name contains Municipal, National, they report to a Ministry, State or Federal Government funded, URL ends in .gov or country code such as .de, .ca, or .ch (e.g., Ministry of Education, China).
Health	Hospitals, Medical Centers, organizations that treat or diagnose patients (e.g., Hospital Aleman)
Healthcare System	Parent organization of a group of hospitals, clinics, or treatment centers (e.g., UNICANCER)
National Academy	Organization co-ordinates scholarly research activities and standards for academic disciplines (e.g., Buenos Aires National Academy of Medicine)
Non-Profit	Registered Charity, Society, NGO, Medical research that is not clinical or part of an Academic institute, URL ends in .org (e.g., World Wildlife Fund)
Partnership	Combination of other institution types, such as Academic & Government, and international collaborations (e.g., International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA))
Research Council	Organization that oversees and provides research policies for public and professional groups (e.g., Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada (SSHRC))
Research Institute	Organizations that are primarily focused on research (e.g., CEA)

Appendix C – Namsor

Namsor develops various tools for origin of names, gender, ethnicity, and types. The database currently contains 7.5 billion names and includes Chinese and Japanese alphabets. The solution applies data mining software, artificial intelligence, and sociolinguistics to extract semantics. Namsor’s technology estimates gender, country of origin ethnicity and residency. Their gender accuracy is approximately 98%. A full description of Namsor methodology and API can be found here: <https://namsor.app/about-us>